

ISic2781

I.Sicily inscription 2781

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Estella Kessler,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contrada Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea",
inventory 12314

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Δαματρ[ί]ου

Apparatus

text of Meligunis Lipára XII

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645178

PHI 334240

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1381.17

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunis Lipára. XII. Le

iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 138
Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1994. Meligunis Lipara VII. Lipari. Contrada
Diana. Scavo XXXVI in proprieta Zagami (1975-1984). Palermo. At no.17 pl.124

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